

Gender Differences in Students' Value System, Engagement, Social Competence, and Cognitive Styles

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Abstract

The value priorities of individuals are influenced by a variety of factors that affect individuals' social behaviors and actions. The present study was conducted to investigate gender differences in students' value systems, Engagement, social competence, and cognitive styles. The statistical population of this study included all undergraduate students at the University of Tehran in the academic year 1397-98. The research sample was 150 male and female students at Tehran University who were selected by stratified random sampling. The value system questionnaire, the engagement of students' scale belongs to Gunuc & Kuzu, Hart's competence perception, and the carton cognitive styles questionnaire were used to collect information. Data were analyzed using a multivariate analysis of variance. The results showed that male students scored higher on material values, cognitive competence, social competence, and physical competence. In using educational strategies and teaching methods, education professionals need to consider the gender and individual disparities of students based on physical, psychological, cultural, and spiritual aspects.

Keywords

Value System, Academic Engagement, Social Competence, Cognitive Styles, Students